

Original Research

Corporate Social Responsibility, Stock Price Crash Risk, Information Asymmetry: A Moderated Perspective

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Abstract

This research aims to examine the impact of information asymmetry on the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and stock price crash risk among 112 companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange from 2018 to 2022. Multiple linear regressions were used to test the hypotheses. The findings indicate a negative and significant relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk. Additionally, the results show that information asymmetry moderates and strengthens the relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk. Consequently, companies that adhere to CSR requirements can reduce the risk of stock price crashes, and in companies with information asymmetry, CSR can further mitigate this risk.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Information Asymmetry, Stock Price Crash Risk.

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Introduction

In today's complex and dynamic world, companies face numerous challenges that can impact their performance and value. One of the most significant of these challenges is the risk of stock price crashes, which can have serious effects on market value and investor confidence. With the acceleration of globalization and technological advancements, capital market instability has intensified, drawing the attention of investors and regulatory bodies to the increasing risk of stock price crashes (Zhang et al., 2024). Research indicates that information opacity and improper disclosure of companies' financial status can lead to increased stock price crash risk (Chen et al., 2001). Stock price crashes can result in significant financial losses for shareholders and pose a threat to the economic system. Therefore, there is considerable interest in strategies to reduce the likelihood of market crashes through the enhancement of corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Feng et al., 2022). CSR is recognized as one of the key elements in improving performance and creating sustainable value. CSR encompasses a set of actions and policies undertaken by companies to improve society, protect the environment, and uphold ethical standards. These activities can include charitable programs, environmental initiatives, and support for local communities, and respect for employee rights (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001). CSR requires companies to consider the social and environmental interests of all stakeholders while generating profits and maintaining legal responsibilities. Historically, CSR was primarily focused on voluntary activities, but its concept has recently become multi-dimensional and often reflects in companies' strategic plans, guiding them towards sustainable performance. The concept of corporate sustainability is often referred to as CSR (Cao et al., 2023; Jo & Harjoto, 2011; Saeidi et al., 2015). As CSR has become a mainstream business activity, it has advanced as a key management area alongside marketing, accounting, or finance (Crane et al., 2013). With many individuals and consumers today being more aware of ethics and moral values, they are more likely to support businesses that align with their personal values. Adhering to CSR represents a commitment to these values. Conversely, irresponsible corporate behavior can damage a company's reputation, lead to loss of future customers, and reduce the company's profits and stock market returns (Govindan et al., 2018). Various studies indicate that companies committed to CSR generally earn greater trust from investors and customers, leading to better financial performance (Carroll, 1999). In this context, examining the relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk holds particular importance. Research shows that companies providing transparent and accurate information about their CSR activities face reduced information asymmetry. This can decrease stock price volatility and ultimately reduce crash risk (Hutton et al., 2009). Information asymmetry refers to a situation where some individuals have more access to information than others. This can lead to incorrect decision-making by investors and affect stock price fluctuations. When companies engage in responsible social activities and provide more transparent information, information asymmetry is reduced, allowing investors to make better decisions (Healy & Palepu, 2001).

Stock price crash risk is defined as the likelihood of a sudden and large-scale decline in a company's stock price (Battaglia et al., 2021), which is explained by specific factors, the most common of which is the sudden release of bad news previously hidden by managers. Managers, concerned about their professional reputation and compensation, conceal bad news from investors. When the bad news accumulates and reaches a tipping

point, all the bad news is suddenly revealed, leading to an abrupt crash in the company's stock price (Hutton et al., 2009). The agency problem, arising from information asymmetry between managers and shareholders, can increase stock price crash risk (Jin & Myers, 2006). Stock price crash risk is a concept aligned with specific company conditions, and all measures used to assess stock price crash risk are based on the residual correlation of company returns with market returns. Therefore, stock price crash risk represents a fall in stock price due to specific company characteristics and does not encompass general market trends. Stock price crash risk is one of the most significant risks that companies face. This risk can affect investor confidence and lead to a decrease in the company's market value. In this context, information asymmetry refers to a situation where some individuals have more access to information than others. This situation can lead to incorrect decision-making by investors and impact stock price volatility. When companies engage in socially responsible activities and provide more transparent information, information asymmetry is reduced, allowing investors to make better decisions (Hutton et al., 2009).

In response to the increasing popularity of CSR in practice, there is a growing interdisciplinary literature on CSR and its impact on corporate actions and outcomes. Numerous studies have examined the relationship between corporate social performance and corporate financial performance (Coelho et al., 2023; Griffin & Mahon, 1997; Sharma & Agarwal, 2022; Suto et al., 2018; Tsatsaronis et al., 2024). Other studies have explored the relationship between CSR and the cost of capital (Bhuiyan & Nguyen, 2020; Chouaibi & Zouari, 2024; El Ghouli et al., 2011; Piórkowska-Kalouźna et al., 2021; Prasad et al., 2022; Setiawan & Yunita, 2023; Suto & Takehara, 2017; Yeh et al., 2020). Some recent studies have examined the relationship between CSR and corporate risk (Farooq et al., 2024; Gao et al., 2023; Jo & Na, 2012; Liu & Luo, 2021; Nguyen & Nguyen, 2015; Rouine et al., 2022). Recent studies show that CSR can play an important role in reducing stock price crash risk (Kim et al., 2014). Companies that pay attention to their social responsibilities may appear more transparent and trustworthy to investors (Dhaliwal et al., 2011). This transparency and trust reduce information asymmetry (Healy & Palepu, 2001). Information asymmetry occurs when key information is unequally distributed between shareholders and managers (Akerlof, 1970). This can lead to incorrect decision-making and consequently increase stock price crash risk (Jin & Myers, 2006).

CSR plays an important role in reducing stock price crash risk. CSR increases transparency, investor trust, and reduces information asymmetry. These actions lead to the long-term sustainability of companies, lower cost of capital, and the attraction and retention of talent. Given the volatility of financial markets, companies need effective strategies to manage financial risks. CSR, as an effective tool, aids in managing these risks and enhancing research interactions. Moreover, the successful implementation of CSR increases trust and transparency in the market and improves companies' relationships with the community. This can contribute to further research development in CSR and financial risks. Further studies in this area can provide new strategies and solutions to reduce stock price crash risk. The results of this research can help company managers and policymakers improve the financial performance and credibility of companies by leveraging CSR and reduce risks related to market fluctuations. Additionally, this research can help better understand the moderating role of information

asymmetry in the relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk (Dhaliwal et al., 2011).

The main objective of this research is to examine the impact of CSR on stock price crash risk and the moderating role of information asymmetry in this relationship. This research aims to achieve a better understanding of these complex relationships through data analysis and providing scientific evidence, and to offer solutions for improving risk management in companies (Kim et al., 2014). Can CSR reduce the risk of stock price crashes? How does information asymmetry affect the relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk? This research will use quantitative methods to collect, describe, and analyze the data. Data related to CSR and stock price crashes will be collected from reputable sources (annual reports, reliable financial databases, and stock exchange databases), and statistical analyses (multiple regression analysis, correlation analysis, and statistical tests) will be conducted to examine the relationships between the variables. This innovative study examines the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and stock crash risk, focusing on the moderating role of information asymmetry. Unlike previous research that primarily explored the direct connection between these variables, this study introduces information asymmetry as a moderating factor, offering fresh insights. By incorporating data from emerging markets, particularly the unique context of the Tehran Stock Exchange and emphasizing practical implications for managers and investors, this research stands out both in terms of subject and application. Furthermore, by adopting a multidimensional approach that bridges CSR and financial risk management, this study contributes to filling existing gaps in the academic literature. Following Chen et al. (2001), Jin and Myers (2006), and Hutton et al. (2009), skewness, as the third moment of specific returns, will be used instead of the mean as the first moment of specific returns or variance as the second moment of specific returns to measure stock price crash risk. This reflects the asymmetry in risk and is important for investment decisions and risk management.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 will be Literature review and hypotheses development, while section 3 will describe the research methods. Section 4 will report the results, and finally, section 5 conclusions discuss the paper.

Literature review and hypothesis development

Despite extensive research on the relationship between CSR and corporate performance, findings are still ambiguous. Agency theory posits that managers of a company act as agents of shareholders and are responsible for pursuing shareholder interests, primarily maximizing profit. Friedman (1970) argues, based on agency theory, that the primary responsibility of a business is to generate profit for its shareholders, and any effort to pursue social or ethical goals beyond profit maximization is inappropriate and unproductive. Hemingway and Maclagan (2004) claim that although CSR can be beneficial for companies in some cases, it can exacerbate company risks, conceal other corporate misdeeds, and hinder long-term or short-term market value and stock market performance. The prevailing view opposes this stance. Freeman (1984) suggests that meeting stakeholder needs enhances a company's reputation in a way that positively impacts its performance, and better fulfillment of CSR conveys more non-financial information, improves corporate governance transparency, and limits managers' short-

term opportunistic behaviors (Eccles et al., 2014; Fatemi et al., 2015; Fernando et al., 2017; Gao et al., 2014; Gelb & Strawser, 2001; Harjoto & Jo, 2011). The agency problem, created by information asymmetry between managers and shareholders, can increase the risk of stock price crashes (Jin & Myers, 2006). Wu et al. (2024) argue that CSR performance, in terms of environmental responsibility and stakeholder responsibility dimensions, can effectively reduce the likelihood of future stock price crashes. However, no significant relationship was found in terms of the social responsibility dimension. Yang et al. (2023) found a negative relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk. Analyst coverage as a moderating variable could not accelerate the positive role of CSR in reducing financial opacity, weakening the negative relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk. This indicates that analysts cannot sufficiently disseminate company-specific information, which in turn exacerbates the information gap between internal and external investors. Fang's (2023) findings indicate that improving CSR helps reduce stock price crash risk. The mediation test shows that enhancing CSR attracts analysts' attention and increases information transparency, thereby reducing stock price crash risk. Institutional ownership and internal control moderate the relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk. Feng et al. (2022) examined the relationships between environmental, social, and governance ratings and stock price crash risk, finding statistically and economically significant negative relationships. Xu et al. (2022) considering information asymmetry and stakeholder theories, investigated the impact of environmental, social, and governance disclosures on future stock price crash risk, finding that these disclosures significantly reduce future stock price crash risk. Wang et al. (2021) reported a positive relationship between banks' social participation and future stock price crash risk. Their study proposed two perspectives to examine this relationship. Signaling theory suggests that high levels of social participation may indicate high ethical standards among bank managers, who are inclined to maintain financial transparency and are less likely to engage in bad news hoarding (i.e., hiding bad news from investors). Therefore, increased social activities are expected to be associated with reduced stock price crash risk. Agency theory, from the perspective of agency costs, suggests that social activities may be used by bank managers as a tool to divert shareholder attention and reduce the likelihood of shareholders exposing managerial misconduct, which may increase bad news hoarding and stock price crash risk in banks. Chen (2020) concluded from empirical research that there is a negative correlation between CSR and stock price crash risk. At the same time, corporate social capital has moderating effects on the relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk. Research findings indicate a significant and negative relationship between CSR and stock price crash risk (Khajavai et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2014; Li, 2016). Based on the above analysis, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

H₁: There is a relationship between corporate social responsibility and stock price crash risk.

H₂: Information asymmetry moderates the relationship between corporate social responsibility and stock price crash risk.

Methodology

Data and sample selection

The initial sample consists of firm-year observations in the Tehran stock exchange database for the period 2018–2022. In order to draw a robust conclusion, we apply the following data filters to prior studies: Firstly, we exclude financial firms as they have a capital structure different from other firms. Secondly, a firm must have at least 30 weeks of stock return data in a fiscal year so that it is included in the sample. Thirdly, we remove firm-year observations missing data in estimating variables. As a result, our sample includes 112 firms and 560 firm-year observations. Secondary data (the data that already existed prior to the current needs of the researcher) has been collected for the purpose of this study. Disclosure of corporate social responsibility data were collected manually from the annual reports, and financial and other data were collected from the Tehran Stock Exchange database. In order to mitigate the effects of outliers, all continuous variables are winsorized at the 1st and 99th percentiles.

Variable description

Explained variables

Stock Price Crash Risk: Stock price crash risk is defined as the likelihood of a sudden and large-scale decline in a company's stock price (Battaglia et al., 2021). Stock price crash risk is explained by specific factors, the most common of which is the sudden release of bad news previously hidden by managers. Managers conceal bad news from investors due to concerns about their professional reputation and compensation. When the bad news accumulates and reaches a tipping point, all the bad news is suddenly revealed, leading to an abrupt crash in the company's stock price. Stock price crash risk is a concept aligned with specific company conditions, and all measures used to assess stock price crash risk are based on the residual correlation of company returns with market returns. Therefore, stock price crash risk represents a fall in stock price due to specific company characteristics and does not encompass general market trends (Hutton et al., 2009). Following Chen et al. (2001); Hutton et al. (2009); Jin and Myers (2006), two measures are used to assess stock price crash risk: the negative conditional skewness of stock returns and down-to-up volatility of stock returns, based on the estimation of company-specific stock returns through an expanded market model that includes lagged and leading conditions for market returns, as described below:

$$r_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 r_{m,t-2} + \beta_2 r_{m,t-1} + \beta_3 r_{m,t} + \beta_4 r_{m,t+1} + \beta_5 r_{m,t+2} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

In the above equation, $r_{i,t}$ represents the weekly return of company i at time t . $r_{m,t}$ represents the weekly market return at time t , and $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ represents the model residual for company i at time t . Then, the company-specific weekly return $R_{i,t}$ is calculated by the residual $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ from model 1 as follows:

$$R_{i,t} = \ln(1 + \varepsilon_{i,t}) \quad (2)$$

Then, two measures of stock price crash risk are calculated as follows:

Down-to-Up Volatility of Stock Returns: Down-to-up volatility is the first indicator of crash risk. The standard deviation of the company-specific weekly returns is calculated for each stock in each year during up weeks when the company-specific weekly returns are above the annual mean and during down weeks when the company-specific weekly returns are below the annual mean. The down-to-up volatility measure is calculated by the logarithm of the ratio of the standard deviation during down weeks to the standard deviation during up weeks, as described in equation 3. In this case, larger down-to-up volatility indicates a more left-skewed distribution of stock returns and consequently a higher likelihood of a crash.

$$DUVol_{i,t} = \ln \left[\frac{(n_{down} - 1) \sum_{down} (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2}{(n_{up} - 1) \sum_{up} (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

In the above equation, n_{up} (n_{down}) represents the number of weeks above (below) the mean for each stock i in year t .

The purpose of this method is to have a better profile of asset volatility since not all volatility is necessarily bad. Positive volatility (price increase) is different from negative volatility (price decrease), and analyzing these two separately helps us to better understand investment risks and opportunities. Steps to calculate down-to-up volatility:

- **Data Collection:** First, collect the asset returns for the desired time period. For example, daily, weekly, or monthly returns.

- **Calculate the Average Return:** Calculate the average return of the asset.

$$\bar{R}_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N R_i \quad (4)$$

- **Separate Returns into Positive and Negative:** Divide the returns into two groups: positive and negative.

n_p : Group of positive returns (Upside)

n_{down} : Group of negative returns (Downside)

- **Calculate the sum of squares of positive and negative standard deviations:**

$$\sum_{up} (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2: \quad \text{For positive returns (Upside Volatility)} \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{down} (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2: \text{ For negative returns (Downside Volatility)} \quad (6)$$

- Calculate down-to-up volatility (ratio of standard deviations):

$$DUVol_{i,t} = \ln \left[\frac{(n_{down} - 1) \sum_{down} (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2}{(n_{up} - 1) \sum_{up} (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2} \right] \quad (7)$$

Negative Conditional Skewness of Stock Returns: The negative conditional skewness of weekly returns for each stock is the second indicator of crash risk. Skewness of stock returns is defined as the third moment of company-specific returns. The following Equation 8 is used to calculate the negative skewness coefficient of stock returns for each company i in a given year. The higher the negative conditional skewness, the greater the company's exposures to stock price crash risk.

$$NCSkew_{i,t} = - \left[\frac{n(n-1)^{3/2} \sum (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^3}{(n-1)(n-2) \left(\sum (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2 \right)^{3/2}} \right] \quad (8)$$

In the above equation, n represents the number of observations of company-specific weekly returns for company i in year t .

Negative conditional skewness measures the balance of the distribution of returns below a certain threshold. This metric is particularly important when assessing costs or losses under critical conditions or large volatility intervals. By using this measure, investors can have a comprehensive view of market risks and adopt better risk management strategies. Steps to calculate negative conditional skewness:

- Data Collection: Gather the daily, weekly, or monthly returns of the stock for the specified period.
- Calculate the Average Return: Calculate the average return of the asset.

$$\bar{R}_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N R_i \quad (9)$$

- Calculate the Sum of Cubes of Deviations: Compute the cubes of deviations of returns from the average return.

$$\sum (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^3 \quad (10)$$

- Calculate the sum of squares of deviations: Compute the sum of squares of deviations of returns from the average return.

$$\sum (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2 \quad (11)$$

- Calculate the negative conditional skewness:

$$NCSkew_{i,t} = - \left[\frac{n(n-1)^{3/2} \sum (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^3}{(n-1)(n-2) \left(\sum (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2 \right)^{3/2}} \right] \quad (12)$$

In the above equation, n represents the sample size - Number of data points in the studied time period. \bar{R}_i represents the average return - Average return of stock i over the study period. $R_{i,t}$ represents the individual return - Return of stock i in period t . $\sum (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^3$ represents the sum of cubes of deviations - Sum of cubes of deviations of returns from the average, indicating the degree of skewness or deviation in the negative range. $\sum (R_{i,t} - \bar{R}_i)^2$ represents the sum of squares of deviations - Sum of squares of deviations of returns from the average. $(n-1, 2)$ represents the correction factors - For more accurate calculation of negative conditional skewness.

Explanatory variables

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): The content analysis method is the most common method used to measure CSR. In content analysis, the researcher uses a coded checklist (Abbott & Mosen, 1979). In most studies, the basis for measuring CSR is the CSR disclosure index based on the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) standards (Martinez-Ferrero et al., 2018). If any of the criteria listed in the GRI standards are mentioned in the CSR report or the annual report of the company, that criterion is assigned a value of one; otherwise, it is assigned a value of zero. The scores are then summed, and the total score is divided by the number of GRI standard criteria. Thus, the value of this variable ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating better efforts by companies to meet GRI standards. In the study by Hasas Yeganeh et al. (2020), a checklist including three dimensions-economic, social, and environmental-and 17 components was used. The required information for the CSR checklist was extracted from the company's annual report and the board of directors' activity report (social performance section).

To calculate CSR using the standardization method, the normalization technique can be used. This method helps to convert the data to a single scale, making comparisons easier and placing the data between 0 and 1. This normalization method converts data values to a specific range (usually between 0 and 1). The steps for CSR standardization are explained below:

Steps for Min-Max Normalization of CSR Data:

- **Data Collection:** Collect CSR data for various companies in different industries and years.
- **Identify Minimum and Maximum Values:** Identify the minimum and maximum CSR values for each industry and year.
- **Normalization Calculation:** Use the normalization formula to convert CSR values to a single scale. One of the common normalization formulas is as follows:

$$CSR_{norm} = \frac{CSR - \min(CSR)}{\max(CSR) - \min(CSR)} \quad (13)$$

In the above equation, CSR_{norm} represents the Normalized CSR value. CSR represents the Initial CSR value. $\min(CSR)$ represents the Minimum CSR value in the industry and year in question. $\max(CSR)$ represents the Maximum CSR value in the industry and year in question.

Moderator variables

Information Asymmetry: The bid-ask spread is used as a measure of information asymmetry (Cao et al., 2023; Cho et al., 2013; Cui et al., 2018; Naqvi et al., 2021). The bid-ask spread refers to the difference between the highest selling price and the lowest buying price in the order book. The following Equation 14 is used to calculate the bid-ask spread.

$$Bid - Ask Spread_{i,d} = - \frac{Ask Price_{i,d} - Bid Price_{i,d}}{Midpoint Price_{i,d}} \quad (14)$$

Where $Bid - Ask Spread_{i,d}$ represents the spread between the bid and ask prices for stock i on day d . $Ask Price_{i,d}$ is the ask price at the end of the trading day for stock i on day d . $Bid Price_{i,d}$ is the bid price at the end of the trading day for stock i on day d . $Midpoint Price_{i,d}$ means the average of the bid and ask prices for stock i on day d . The information asymmetry for stock i in year t is calculated by the average daily bid-ask spread for stock i in year t , respectively.

Control variables

Based on previous studies, the factors that influence stock crash risk are considered as control variables (Andreou et al., 2016; Fang, 2023; Habib et al., 2018; Kim & Zhang, 2016; Yang et al., 2023). The natural logarithm of total assets (Size) indicates the size of the company. The ratio of total debt to total assets (Lev) is used to control the effect of financial leverage. The company's age (Age) indicates the length of time since the company's establishment. The market-to-book ratio (M/B) is obtained by dividing the market value by the book value of the company. Profitability (ROA) or return on assets is obtained by dividing profit by total assets. Dummy variables for industry and year are also used to control for industry-specific and year-specific factors.

Statistical models

Based on the studies conducted by Hao et al. (2018), Kim et al. (2014), Wu and Ho (2019), Wu et al. (2024), and Yang et al. (2023), the following model is proposed to examine the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and stock crash risk:

To test Hypotheses 1, this study estimated the following model as Model 1:

$$Crash_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CSR_{i,t} + \beta_j \sum_{j=1}^5 Control\ variables_{i,t} + Industry_i + Year_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (15)$$

The following model, based on Baron and Kenny (1986), is used to examine the moderating effect of information asymmetry on the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and stock crash risk:

$$Crash_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CSR_{i,t} + \beta_2 Spread_{i,t} + \beta_3 (CSR \times Spread)_{i,t} + \beta_j \sum_{j=1}^5 control\ variables_{i,t} + Industry_i + Year_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (16)$$

In these equations, $Crash_{i,t}$ represents the risk of stock price crash, $CSR_{i,t}$ denotes the corporate social responsibility. $Spread_{i,t}$ is the measure of information asymmetry, $(CSR \times Crash)_{i,t}$ is the interaction variable of corporate social responsibility and stock crash risk, $\sum_{j=1}^5 Control\ variables_{i,t}$ is the vector of control variables, $Industry_i$ is the vector of dummy variables to control for industry differences, $Year_t$ is the vector of dummy variables to control for year differences, and $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is the error term. We have compared several regression methods for the panel data, including the fixed-effects model (within estimators), the random-effects model, and pooled OLS estimators. Based on the performance of the models, we eventually chose fixed-effects model estimators as our estimation model.

Experimental results

This section introduces descriptive statistics for the data and samples employed in this study, and report the results of the hypothesis tests.

Descriptive analysis

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for the variables used in the regression analysis. The mean values of the stock crash risk measures, the down-to-up volatility measure, and the negative conditional skewness of stock returns are 1.08 and -0.22, respectively. The mean value of corporate social responsibility (CSR) is 0.65. The mean value of the bid-ask spread is 0.45. The mean size of the companies is 14.05. The mean financial leverage

is 0.60. The mean age of the sample companies is 32.91. The mean market-to-book ratio is 3.43. The mean return on assets (ROA) is 0.12.

Table 1. Descriptive analysis

No.	Variable	Mean	Median	Max	Min	S.D
1	DUVol	1.083	0.940	5.157	0.094	0.631
2	NCSkew	-0.220	-0.185	-0.011	-6.822	0.433
3	CSR	0.645	0.615	1.000	0.000	0.125
4	Spread	0.454	0.184	3.498	0.000	0.616
5	Size	14.056	13.905	19.150	11.035	1.295
6	Lev	0.604	0.588	2.773	0.067	0.254
7	Age	32.911	34.000	62.000	8.000	15.767
8	M/B	3.434	2.355	107.010	0.000	7.154
9	ROA	0.120	0.102	0.670	-0.806	0.167

Pearson's Correlation

Correlation analysis examines the initial relationship between variables (univariate analysis), and based on the results in Table 2, it can be said that there is a relationship between the variables, and a more detailed examination of these relationships can be performed. Table 2 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients of the variables in the models. Since all coefficients have absolute values less than 0.9 (Table 2), severe multicollinearity is not expected in the models. The variance inflation factor (VIF) test shows that the maximum VIF is 1.49, indicating the absence of severe multicollinearity in the models. All variables (based on the augmented Dickey-Fuller test) are at a significant level.

Table 2. Pearson correlation matrix

No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	1.000								
2	0.565***	1.000							
3	0.048***	-0.050***	1.000						
4	0.112***	0.110***	0.062	1.000					
5	0.030***	0.033***	-0.102***	0.056***	1.000				
6	0.022***	0.020***	-0.065***	0.014***	-0.010***	1.000			
7	-0.057***	0.060***	0.003***	0.004***	0.045***	-0.041	1.000		
8	0.042***	-0.040***	0.072***	-0.029***	-0.063***	0.115***	0.023**	1.000	
9	0.106***	0.110***	-0.050***	-0.018***	0.235***	-0.618	0.039**	-0.011**	1.000

Note: *, **, and *** denote 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels, respectively.

Multivariate analysis

The results of the panel data regression that examine the impact of information asymmetry on the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and stock crash risk are presented in Table 3. In this study, regression analysis is conducted to test the relationships between dependent and independent variables. The ordinary least squares (OLS) method is used after checking for multicollinearity, stationarity, normality, linearity, and serial correlation.

Table 3. Results of regression analyses

Dependent Variable	DUVol	DUVol	NCSkew	NCSkew
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
C	8.963*(1.88)	9.035*(1.88)	0.314(1.50)	0.245(1.44)
CSR	-0.158**(-1.98)	-0.178**(-1.99)	-0.123**(-1.97)	-0.133***(-2.90)
Spread		0.423**(2.54)		0.211**(5.38)
CSR*Spread		-0.046***(-3.52)		-0.030**(-4.23)
Size	-2.106**(-2.07)	-2.085**(-2.04)	0.033**(2.24)	0.031**(2.30)
Lev	0.863**(2.48)	0.851**(2.46)	-0.199(-1.03)	-0.198**(-2.37)
Age	0.136(1.54)	0.136(1.54)	-0.001**(3.33)	-0.010(-6.67)
M/B	-0.022**(-2.59)	-0.022(-1.59)	0.210**(2.50)	0.010***(-2.90)
ROA	2.765** (2.72)	2.767** (2.71)	0.091** (2.93)	0.094** (2.99)
Industry fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES
A R-squared	0.271	0.270	0.241	0.211
F- statistic	1.420***	1.394***	2.750***	1.980***

Note: *, **, and*** denote 10%, 5%, and 1% significance levels, respectively.

In Table 3, according to Model 1, the coefficient of CSR is -0.158 and is significant at the 5% level, indicating an inverse relationship between CSR and down-to-up volatility (stock price crash risk). The results support the view that CSR disclosure reduces the likelihood of stock price crashes (Hypothesis 1) and aligns with the argument that CSR disclosure significantly minimizes stock price crash risk (Cao et al., 2023; Chen, 2020; Wu et al., 2024). According to signaling theory, CSR disclosure can help reduce information asymmetry and thus lower the likelihood of stock price crashes (Wu & Ho, 2019). This shows that companies, by reporting CSR activities through sustainability reports, can present a favorable image to shareholders, investors, and the community. Hence, CSR disclosure can be a savior for companies in risk and crisis situations. In Model 2, given that the absolute value of the sum of the CSR coefficient (-0.178) and the interaction term coefficient of CSR and bid-ask spread (-0.046) is greater than the absolute value of the CSR coefficient (-0.178), information asymmetry strengthens the inverse relationship between CSR and down-to-up volatility (stock price crash risk)

(Hypothesis 2). The results are consistent with recent studies (Cao et al., 2023). In Model 3, the CSR coefficient is -0.123 and is significant at the 5% level, indicating an inverse relationship between CSR and negative conditional skewness (stock price crash risk). In Model 4, given that the absolute value of the sum of the CSR coefficient (-0.133) and the interaction term coefficient of CSR and bid-ask spread (-0.030) is greater than the absolute value of the CSR coefficient (-0.133), information asymmetry strengthens the inverse relationship between CSR and negative conditional skewness (stock price crash risk).

Conclusion, Implications and Limitations

It is concerning that managers may use CSR disclosure for their own purposes, such as hiding negative news and increasing risk. However, CSR disclosure can improve company performance and reduce risk if it benefits shareholders and other stakeholders. Therefore, existing research has produced mixed results, and further studies are necessary. The aim of this study is to determine the relationship between CSR disclosure and stock price crash risk and to evaluate the moderating role of information asymmetry on this relationship.

This study uses a sample of 112 companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange from 2018 to 2022. The findings of this research indicate that corporate social responsibility (CSR) contributes to reducing stock crash risk, but this effect is highly influenced by information asymmetry. Our results emphasize that in situations with high levels of information asymmetry, the relationship between CSR and reduced stock crash risk becomes stronger. In other words, under conditions of information asymmetry, high-quality CSR can have a significant impact in mitigating stock crash risk. This underscores the critical role of informational transparency in enhancing the effectiveness of CSR efforts. This highlights the importance of non-financial data in sustainability reports of companies in developing countries. If companies are committed to high transparency standards in financial reporting and therefore less inclined to hoard bad news, CSR actions are expected to be associated with lower stock price crash risk. Conversely, if managers use CSR to cover bad news and divert shareholder attention, CSR could be associated with higher crash risk.

This study contributes to the growing literature on CSR and its implications for companies and investors. It focuses on the unique role of CSR in reducing stock price crash risk and provides new evidence on the economic consequences of CSR. By identifying information asymmetry as a moderating variable, this study extends previous research by identifying a new factor that strengthens the negative relationship between CSR and future stock price crash risk.

These results have important implications for managers and policymakers. Firstly, companies should prioritize improving reporting systems and enhancing informational transparency alongside investing in CSR activities. Secondly, investors should consider not only a company's CSR initiatives but also the existing level of information asymmetry when assessing stock crash risk. Finally, policymakers can create regulations that reduce information asymmetry, fostering an environment where companies can fully benefit from their CSR initiatives. By combining theoretical and practical insights, this study

highlights the complexity of the relationship between CSR, information asymmetry, and stock crash risk, and offers suggestions for future research, including exploring the impact of other environmental and organizational factors on this relationship. Although this study has significant theoretical and practical importance, there are still limitations. Firstly, the measurement of variables should be improved to ensure research reliability. Since there is no single non-financial index for measuring CSR domestically, this study uses scoring of CSR reports to measure the level of this variable based on existing research. Although the scoring is relatively comprehensive and valid, there is a certain degree of subjectivity that needs improvement. In the future, using appropriate measurement methods for conducting empirical research is essential. Secondly, this study lacks systematic research on the role of other internal and external governance factors. In the future, more attention might be paid to the differing roles of independent directors and institutional investors, as well as internal management rights, external media, organizational environment, and other factors. Future research could examine the impact of CSR performance dimensions on various aspects of company operations, such as supply chain management and risk management, or stock market indicators like liquidity risk.

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